

Behavioral Ethograms in Companion Animals as Early Indicators of Potential Zoonotic Targets: A One Health Framework

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Abstract

Diagnosis of zoonotic diseases is often delayed until the onset of specific clinical symptoms, highlighting the need for early, novel diagnostic methods. This conceptual review, by examining the neuroimmune pathways activated in the early stages of infection and their probable impact on companion animal behavior, tries to introduce behavioral biomarkers as a potential, accessible, early, and cost-effective diagnostic method. The selected zoonotic diseases in this article are proposed as candidate models for the study of behavioral biomarkers and designing ethograms. This approach, within the framework of a One Health perspective, emphasizes the integration of behavioral surveillance with veterinary and public health strategies and provides a foundation for future research on early and noninvasive diagnosis of zoonotic diseases.

Keywords: Zoonotic disease, Behavioral biomarkers, Companion animals, Ethogram, One health, Neuroinflammation

Introduction

The outbreak of zoonoses has become one of the most central global health challenges in recent decades, and according to World Health Organization estimates, more than 60% of human infectious diseases and about 75% of emerging pathogens are of animal origin(1). Also the intensity of human-animal contact, climate change, international movements, and the expansion of host ranges have caused the threat of zoonoses to not only persist but also spread at a faster rate and in new patterns(2). In such a scenario, companion animals have become one of the most important potential drivers for the transmission of pathogens between animals and humans due to their close interaction with humans. This situation

highlights the need for innovative strategies for early detection and monitoring of zoonoses dynamics more than ever(3).

Although current laboratory diagnostic methods, from PCR to serology, are considered the gold standard, their reliance on clinical symptoms often delays zoonotic disease detection until mid- or late stages, when microbial load and transmission risk are high. Additionally, high laboratory costs, limited home access, and dependence on clinic visits restrict continuous monitoring, creating a gap between disease onset and diagnosis that current tools cannot bridge(4).

Animal ethology has traditionally been used to analyze social dynamics and assess animal welfare, while growing scientific evidence indicates that zoonotic pathogens may systematically alter animal behavioral patterns, including changes in mood, activity, sociability, appetite, sleep–wake cycles, and arousal thresholds(5). As a result, the development and validation of behavioral ethograms as “non-invasive biomarkers” could provide a new method for early detection of zoonoses(6).

The One Health approach in this study highlights the interconnectedness of human, animal, and environmental health. Behavioral ethograms are proposed as practical, cost-effective tools for early zoonosis detection, especially in domestic settings where formal diagnostics are often delayed. This method enables easy and repeatable monitoring and can integrate with veterinary, public health, and environmental systems as an additional early-warning layer in zoonotic disease prediction(7).

Targeted zoonoses in this article were selected based on clinical and epidemiological significance and the existence of a valid scientific background relevant to the research objectives. To maintain a scientific framework, priority was given to common and important zoonotic diseases that had sufficient scientific evidence of their neurotropism and early impact on the neuro-immune system. This approach provides a solid foundation for proposing them as candidates for behavioral biomarker studies and developing standard behavioral protocols, while keeping the article limited to a conceptual and basic review.

This article first describes the theoretical framework of behavioral ethograms as potential non-invasive biomarkers for the diagnosis of zoonoses. The available evidence on pathogens that may affect animal behavior will then be reviewed, and a proposed conceptual model for standardizing, validating, and integrating these ethograms into One Health systems will be presented. Finally, future research directions and the translational potential of this approach in home diagnostics, epidemiology, and health policy are reviewed.

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Methodological Approach

This conceptual review attempts not to just collect quantitative data but to develop theoretical frameworks, integrate scattered evidence, and bridge interdisciplinary fields. To collect references, a narrative search was conducted in PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science databases. Keywords such as "behavioral markers," "zoonoses," "early detection," "sentinel animals," "neurotropic zoonoses," "One Health," and combinations related to veterinary medicine, immunology, epidemiology, and animal behavior were used. The search period was flexible but the main focus was on studies published in the last decade, although more classical sources were included when necessary to complete the theoretical background. International organizations (WHO, OIE, and CDC) reports were also reviewed. Evidence-supported studies that were relevant to the main question of the review and have clear methodology and deeper interdisciplinary analysis were prioritized. The source selection process did not involve strict systematic criteria due to the conceptual nature of the study, and the emphasis was on theoretical comprehensiveness and interdisciplinary coherence.

1. Foundations of Behavioral Biomarkers in Companion Animals

Behavior is known to be an early reflection of physiological changes and may therefore be used as a non-invasive biomarker for early monitoring of zoonotic diseases. This perspective, which has its roots in evolutionary biology, behavioral neuroscience, and neuroimmunology, is based on the assumption that physiological disorders, especially those caused by inflammation and early activation of the immune response, produce detectable changes in behavioral performance before the development of classic clinical signs(8). In the One Health framework, this point becomes more important because companion animals are part of human life, and the slightest change in their health status can provide valuable information about the pathogenic trends circulating in the shared human-animal environment(9).

1.1 Behavior as Subclinical Biomarkers

Behavioral biomarkers are a set of subtle, persistent, and often imperceptible changes in animal behavior that could occur before the classic signs of disease appear or before the animal meets the clinical criteria for diagnosis. These behavioral patterns are the initial outcome of interactions between the immune system, brain, and neuroendocrine axes—

interactions that can begin long before detectable tissue damage or the onset of a clinical syndrome. Therefore, these behavioral changes may not be considered a late consequence of the disease but rather the first observable level of physiological dysfunction(10).

These changes are more important in the case of zoonotic diseases, which often have long incubation periods, nonspecific initial manifestations, and inflammatory-based pathophysiology(11). Mild activation of the immune system can dramatically alter an animal's behavioral patterns, even though there may be no detectable physical, laboratory, or clinical signs at this stage. This behavior is earlier, more sensitive, and more environment-dependent than conventional biological indicators. Some behaviors, such as decreased playfulness, decreased curiosity, increased withdrawal, subtle changes in stance or gait, decreased response speed, decreased grooming, or transient changes in appetite, are examples that often may precede fever, lymphadenitis, weight change, or other clinical signs. This phenomenon is not limited to domesticated mammals; similar evidence has been seen in birds, reptiles, and even primates, indicating that behavioral changes can appear before measurable physiological indicators(12).

1.2 Evolutionary Basis of Sickness Behavior

Sickness behaviors are coordinated sets of behavioral changes such as lethargy, anorexia, social withdrawal, and sleep disturbance that may no longer be considered nonspecific consequences of infection-induced weakness; rather, they can be evolutionary adaptive strategies that have evolved in various animal species to increase survival when exposed to pathogens. Classical evolutionary studies have shown that these behavioral changes serve to redistribute energy toward the effective execution of immune responses (such as fever and acute phase proteins) and, at the same time, reduce the likelihood of pathogen transmission in the population by reducing social contact(13). Thus, illness-related behavior is the result of an evolutionary trade-off, reducing costly and unnecessary activities (exploration, play, reproduction) in exchange for increasing the chance of survival during infection.

From an evolutionary-mechanistic perspective, the universality and similarity of these behaviors in vertebrates is due to the conservation of neuroimmune pathways that translate environmental immune signals into behavioral patterns in the central nervous system (CNS)(14).

The evolutionary purpose of this mechanism is to regulate neural regions that regulate energy, motivation, and social behavior (hypothalamus, limbic, and mesolimbic dopamine

pathways) that are biologically flexible and naturally associated with homeostatic and immune signals. This feature can make them ideal locations for rapid and coordinated behavioral changes when faced with a pathogenic threat, without the need for extensive genetic changes during evolution(15).

Evolution has also shaped the context-dependence and reversibility of these behaviors. For example, short-term anorexia and social isolation can be beneficial for survival, but prolonged inflammation or immune responses can be detrimental (reduced feeding opportunities, loss of social and reproductive interactions). Therefore, natural selection has selected pathways that, in addition to a rapid response to danger, adjust the intensity of behavior in proportion to the intensity of immune stimulation and provide the possibility of returning to normal behavior after the pathogenic threat is eliminated(16).

1.3 Companion Animals as Sentinel Hosts

The role of companion animals is important not only because of their biological and environmental proximity to humans, but also because many of the common pathological factors between them and humans traverse similar neuroimmune pathways. In this perspective, the companion animal can be a “behavioral sentinel,” an animal whose early exposure to a pathogen may produce behavioral patterns that can serve as an early warning before disease manifests in humans or the wider population. This capacity can only be understood if behavior is seen not as a superficial phenomenon but as a systematic output of neural, immune, and metabolic networks(17).

One reason that behavior can appear before physical symptoms is the time-consuming nature of classical tissue and physiological changes; while neuronal networks and mediator pathways such as cytokines, prostaglandins, and the HPA axis can change on an hourly scale, the animal may show small but significant changes in social interaction, activity level, sleep-wakefulness, stimulus tolerance, or exploratory behaviors before fever, anorexia, or tissue damage develops. This is where standardized behavioral ethograms can come into play as a measurement tool, capturing patterns of change in a structured manner rather than relying on scattered observations. Another important factor is the higher biological susceptibility of many companion animals to certain pathogens than humans, during which behavior may be the only detectable marker. The difference in sensitivity makes companion animals appear as a “natural biosensor” (any slight change in the level of environmental contamination, vector network, or intensity of pathogen circulation is first reflected in their behavior, even if no diagnostic signs or definite risk to humans are yet observable)(18). (Table 1)

Table 1. Conceptual Comparative Framework for Companion Animals as Sentinel Hosts for Emerging Zoonoses

Domain	Dogs (<i>Canis familiaris</i>)	Cats (<i>Felis catus</i>)
Ecological Interface	High exposure to outdoor vectors (ticks, sandflies, mosquitoes); frequent human–environment bridging through walks and shared public spaces	Greater interaction with micro-habitats, small wildlife, and arthropod reservoirs due to predatory behavior and roaming
Human–Animal Contact Dynamics	Intense physical contact; high likelihood of owner noticing subtle behavioral changes	Often subtle, species-specific behaviors; owners may miss early signs unless trained
Baseline Behavioral Stability	More consistent routines (sleep, activity, feeding), thus deviations are easier to detect	Broader baseline variability; changes in behavior may require more precise criteria to differentiate normal vs. pathological
Early Behavioral Signals	Reduced play, decreased social engagement, altered gait, avoidance of physical contact	Increased hiding, reduced grooming, changes in vocalization, altered predatory interest
Sensory & Neurobiological Reactivity	Strong nociceptive vocalization and overt behavioral withdrawal during early inflammatory states	More cryptic sickness behaviors; may display hypoactivity instead of overt avoidance
Environmental Risk Integration	Better reflect vector abundance and environmental pathogen load at community level	Better reflect micro-reservoir fluctuations and indoor environmental risks
Owner Observability	High—changes often recognized quickly due to proximity and routine interactions	Moderate—owners may overlook subtle deviations unless prompted by education
Typical Onset Window for Subclinical Behavioral Changes	Short latency and often more pronounced due to social nature	Early onset but more subtle, often preceding physiological signs by days to weeks
Integration with One Health Surveillance	Suitable for community-level environmental alerts	Suitable for household-level and indoor pathogen circulation alerts
Criteria for a Valid Sentinel Behavioral Marker	Clear deviation from routine, repeatable across days, linked to known neuroimmune axes, and reversible after pathogen clearance	Detectable change relative to individualized baseline, species-consistent patterns, low likelihood of being caused by stress-only phenomena

This information is more important from the perspective of behavioral pathology. Behavior can be monitored by the animal's owners in the same home environment without the need for specialized instruments, unlike hematological or imaging markers(19).

At the population level, companion animals are a window into what is happening in micro-ecosystems that veterinary healthcare systems do not typically receive data from. The companion animal is a living data point that is exposed daily to a complex network of vectors, reservoirs, environmental pathogens, temperature changes, and biological interactions. Therefore, any sustained behavioral change in these animals actually may represent an ecological signal (a new pathogen has entered the environment, or the intensity of transmission of a known agent has increased, or the status of vectors is changing)(20).

From a One Health perspective, the position of sentinel animals is important not only in the early detection of disease but also in changing human behavior. Early behavioral changes in pets can increase owner awareness, prompt veterinary visits and environmental screening, and prevent further contact with vectors. This behavioral loop is a natural protective mechanism that, if systematized, can be an important part of zoonoses surveillance and control strategies in urban and semi-rural communities(21).

In conclusion, using behavior as a non-invasive indicator may not be simply a veterinary tool but an integrated strategy in population health. Interpreting behavior as an integrated output of biological systems, examining companion animals as early warning receptors, and relying on the early nature of neuroimmune changes are a set of reasons that may form the scientific basis for the use of behavioral ethograms as early biomarkers of zoonoses(22).

2. Neurobiological Basis of Early Behavioral Changes

Behavioral changes in companion animals reflect the complex interaction between the immune system and the nervous system (the neuro-immune interface)(23). (Table 2)

2.1 Innate Immunity and Neuroimmune Signaling

In the early stages of most zoonotic diseases, the peripheral immune system can be activated by pathogen recognition by pattern recognition receptors (PRRs), including Toll-like receptors (TLRs), NOD-like receptors (NLRs), and RIG-I-like receptors (RLRs) on macrophages and dendritic cells. This activation leads to the widespread secretion of inflammatory cytokines such as interleukin-1 beta (IL-1 β), interleukin-6 (IL-6), tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), and interferon-gamma (IFN- γ). Immune signals released into

the environment reach the central nervous system through several distinct but overlapping pathways and can shape the early behavioral patterns of the disease(24).

2.1.1 Neural pathway

The first pathway is the direct neural axis via the vagus nerve; vagal afferent terminals, which contain IL-1 receptor (IL-1R) and TNF receptor (TNFR) receptors in the liver and intestine, send signals to the nucleus of the solitary tract (NST) in response to cytokines, and this nucleus, after integrating the messages, transmits its excitation to higher areas such as the parabrachial nucleus and then the hypothalamus. In this pathway, the central nervous system is informed of environmental changes and induces a set of behaviors associated with the disease, including decreased appetite, decreased activity level, increased sleepiness, and decreased social interaction(25).

2.1.2 Humoral pathway

In the second pathway, inflammatory cytokines can enter central structures without crossing the blood-brain barrier and through areas of the brain that naturally lack this barrier (circumventricular organs/CVOs). These areas include the area postrema, the organum vasculosum of the lamina terminalis (OVLT), and the subfornical organ (SFO), which are highly permeable to environmental factors and soluble molecules(26).

Once cytokines enter these areas, inflammatory signals are rapidly transmitted to neuroendocrine regulatory nuclei and behavioral regulatory centers. This transmission causes changes in neurochemical balance (particularly the serotonergic, dopaminergic, and noradrenergic pathways) and activation of circuits responsible for the manifestation of disease behaviors, including decreased appetite, decreased activity, altered sleep cycles, decreased social interaction, and increased sensitivity to threat(27).

Like the neural pathway, this pathway allows the body to translate a peripheral inflammatory signal into a rapid and coordinated behavioral response, but its effect is more widespread and systemic, and it plays an important role in the persistence of disease responses in the longer stages of infection(28).

The arrival of these signals activates endothelial cells and increases the production of prostaglandins (especially PGE₂), which play a key role in the modulation of fever and disease behaviors(29). These inflammatory lipoproteins at the CNS level cause a feeling of fatigue, reduced motivation, and motor disorders and act as key mediators of the immune

system-behavior relationship. At the same time, neurotransmitter pathways such as serotonin, dopamine, and norepinephrine, which are involved in the control of mood, motivation, and response to stimuli, are affected by immune signals and exacerbate behavioral changes(30).

2.1.3 Cellular pathway

The third transmission pathway is the cellular pathway; peripheral inflammation increases the expression of adhesion molecules such as intercellular adhesion molecule-1 (ICAM-1) and vascular cell adhesion molecule-1 (VCAM-1) on endothelial cells and facilitates the migration of activated monocytes into the brain. These cells transform into microglia-like cells in the central nervous system and, by producing cytokines, nitric oxide, and prostaglandins, can alter the composition of neuronal activity in areas regulating mood, memory, motivation, and social behavior(31).

2.2 Central Integrative Response: HPA Axis Activation

Following the three neural, humoral, and cellular pathways, activation of the hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal axis (HPA Axis) plays a central role in these behavioral changes. HPA activation leads to increased secretion of glucocorticoids, which have systemic effects on immunity and central effects on behavior and cognition(32). This response, in interaction with cytokines and neurotransmitters, can cause decreased activity, anorexia, decreased social interactions, and changes in sleep–wake patterns, all of which are early indicators of behavioral disturbance(33). (Figure 1)

2.3 Central Integrative Responses and Neuroimmune Interactions

Once the brain receives these signals, several brain regions integrate this information and translate it into behavioral changes. The hypothalamus is responsible for both energy balance and thermoregulation, activation of the hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal (HPA) axis, through its nuclei, including the arcuate nucleus of the hypothalamus (ARH), the preoptic area of the hypothalamus (POA), and the paraventricular nucleus (PVN)(34). Activation of the HPA axis leads to the secretion of corticotropin-releasing hormone (CRH), an increase in adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH), and ultimately an increase in glucocorticoid levels(35). In addition, limbic structures such as the amygdala, hippocampus, and bed nucleus of the stria terminalis (BNST) integrate inflammatory messages with emotional processing and produce changes in anxiety, learning, social reactivity, and motivation(36). The

mesolimbic dopamine system, consisting of the ventral tegmental area (VTA) and nucleus accumbens (NAc), is also prominently affected by inflammation(37); reduced dopamine activity in this pathway promotes decreased motivation and anhedonia, explaining the decreased social interactions and decreased exploratory behaviors(38).

At the molecular level, cytokines alter the tryptophan–kynurenine pathway by activating the enzyme indoleamine-2,3-dioxygenase (IDO)(39). As a result, tryptophan is converted primarily to kynurenine metabolites rather than to serotonin; the reduction in serotonin, along with the increase in neurotoxic metabolites such as 3-hydroxykynurenine (3-HK) and quinolinic acid (QUIN), exacerbates inflammation-related mood and cognitive disorders(40). In addition, activation of microglia increases glutamate release and decreases its uptake by astrocytes, which ultimately leads to hyperexcitability in the hippocampus and amygdala, leading to anxiety, exaggerated defensive behaviors, and learning deficits(41). Under conditions of chronic inflammation, microglia enter a primed state, which means an exaggerated response to mild stimuli, and this phenomenon can explain the escalating episodes of potential behavioral disorders in chronic zoonotic diseases(42). In addition to the above mechanisms, visceral sensory pathways also play a prominent role in behavioral changes. Inflammation or infection in visceral tissues stimulates sensory vagal terminals and transmits visceral pain messages via the NTS and parabrachial nuclei to the insular cortex; the result is decreased appetite, altered gait, decreased activity, and the emergence of conservative behaviors. Cross-regulation between cytokines and the opioid system also lowers pain thresholds by altering the sensitivity of μ -opioid receptors and exacerbates behaviors associated with physical discomfort(43). Furthermore, social avoidance in many zoonoses serves as an evolutionarily conserved defensive behavior to reduce pathogen transmission and allocate energy to immune processes(44). Importantly, these behavioral patterns are often observable weeks before the onset of clinical symptoms and may produce a series of subtle but persistent changes in activity, social interaction, sleep cycles, sensory reactivity, and even vocalization that can be used as preclinical windows and valuable behavioral biomarkers for the early diagnosis of zoonoses(45).

Key to understanding early illness behaviors are the simultaneous and networked interplay between cytokines, prostaglandins, the HPA axis, and neurotransmitters. Early behavioral changes are the integrated output of these molecular and neural pathways. Whether in viral or parasitic infections, these pathways suggest that behavior cannot be a random response but a coherent, systemic reflection of neurobiological and immune changes(46).

Table 2. Probable Behavioral Outputs Associated With Key Neuroimmune Pathways in Early Zoonotic Infections (A Putative Model)

Neuroimmune Pathway	Primary Mechanism	Associated Behavioral Signature
Peripheral cytokine surge (\uparrow IL-1 β , TNF- α , IL-6)	Activation of peripheral immune receptors and cytokine signaling to the CNS	Hyporexia, reduced activity, increased sleepiness, social withdrawal, irritability
Afferent vagal signaling	Direct transmission of inflammatory signals to the nucleus tractus solitarius (NTS) \rightarrow hypothalamus	Lethargy, decreased motivation, altered sleep-wake cycle, reduced grooming
Cytokine entry via circumventricular organs (lacking BBB)	Stimulation of CVO structures and central inflammatory sensing	Anorexia, restlessness, increased need for rest, decreased responsiveness to environmental stimuli
Monocyte trafficking into the CNS	Microglial activation and amplification of neuroinflammation	Anxiety-like behavior, reduced exploratory activity, avoidance, altered defensive responses
Hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis activation (CRH \rightarrow ACTH \rightarrow cortisol)	Systemic stress response and energy redistribution	Stress-like behaviors, heightened sensitivity to noise/movement, reduced owner interaction
Disruption of mesolimbic dopaminergic pathway (VTA-NAc)	Decreased dopamine release and impaired reward processing	Anhedonia, reduced play behavior, diminished pursuit of rewarding stimuli, psychomotor slowing
Tryptophan-kynurenine pathway shift (\uparrow IDO activity)	Decreased serotonin availability; increase in neuroactive kynurenine metabolites	Low mood, decreased behavioral flexibility, mild compulsive behaviors
Central glutamatergic dysregulation	Increased neuronal excitability and excessive glutamate activity	Exaggerated defensive behaviors, irritability, hyper-reactivity to stimuli
Visceral nociceptive signaling	Transmission of visceral pain via vagal pathways	Abnormal posture, reluctance to jump, reduced mobility, atypical vocalization
Altered endogenous opioid system	Lowered pain threshold and dysregulated analgesia	Sensitivity to touch, withdrawal, discomfort-associated movement
Hypothalamic sleep regulation changes	POA activation and altered sleep-regulatory hormones	Excessive sleep or fragmented sleep, reduced daytime activity

Fig. 1. Schematic putative overview of pathogen entry, immune activation, and early CNS-mediated behavioral changes.

3. Preclinical Behavioral Indicators and Ethogram Design

Ethograms are standardized and systematic tools for recording animal behavior over a period of time, allowing the identification of behavioral patterns associated with physiological changes and disease(47). As animal behaviors may often be the earliest visible indicators of nervous and immune system responses to infection or inflammation, ethograms can detect behavioral changes before clinical signs appear and allow for early, non-invasive pathogen detection, especially within the framework of One Health and zoonotic disease surveillance.

The selected behaviors should be based on scientific principles, be sensitive to biological changes, be sufficiently reproducible, and be related to neuroimmune pathways. General activity levels, social interactions, sleep-wake patterns, exploratory behaviors, eating and drinking habits, and responses to sensory stimuli are among the most probable common

indicator behaviors. By recording these behaviors continuously and systematically, researchers can extract quantitative data, compare different animal groups, and develop standardized ethograms.

For designing an ethogram, the behaviors should be clearly defined, the observation conditions should be specified, the recording duration determined, and the data properly quantified. Recording relevant behaviors with minimal observer bias strengthens the scientific validity of ethograms and enhances their practical use in early disease monitoring, enabling veterinarians and animal caregivers to intervene without delay(48).

4. Behavioral Indicators in Selected Zoonoses

The selection of this set of diseases was based on their neurotropic nature that makes them potential for early neuroimmune changes prior to the onset of clinical signs. These significant zoonoses can ensure coverage across major neurotropic pathogen groups (viruses, and parasites) and serve as candidates for future research, facilitating early detection through behavioral biomarkers.

4.1 Influenza A subtype of H5N1

Highly pathogenic avian influenza is a neurotropic virus(49). This zoonotic disease has been associated with encephalitis and prominent neurological disorders in both birds and a range of wild and domestic mammals(50,51).

Despite its respiratory-gastrointestinal origin, experimental models and field necropsies indicate H5N1 can invade the CNS via the olfactory nerve and replicate in the olfactory mucosa and bulb before invading the respiratory system(52).

Numerous outbreak reports show early behavioral changes due to neural manifestations, such as ataxia, tremors, decreased responsiveness, and altered locomotion, more prominent than classic respiratory lesions at presentation or at necropsy(53).

The importance of these changes is not only pathological but also from an epidemiological perspective(54). Furthermore, the diversity of susceptible hosts (from chickens and turkeys to cats, dogs, foxes, and even dolphins) provides a unique opportunity to compare behavioral patterns across multiple species and probably show that, regardless of species differences, a common primary behavioral syndrome may appear in all of them, including decreased arousal, impaired coordination, and decreased responsiveness to stimuli(55–58).

This behavioral link between the animal reservoir and human risk may introduce H5N1, a unique model that can demonstrate that behavior is not a secondary symptom but a primary biomarker of zoonosis.

4.2 Toxoplasmosis

Toxoplasma gondii is an obligate intracellular protozoan(59). Both acute and chronic stages are capable of affecting the structure and function of the nervous system(60). The entry of the parasite into the animal's body, whether through the oral route or through environmental contact, in some cases may be accompanied by a very mild acute phase(61). In the first days, the parasite initiates a relatively slow but directional transmission to the brain via dendrites and cellular tropism pathways(62), simultaneously causing mild inflammation that may alter neuronal pathways associated with fear, disgust, decision-making, and sensory perception. These changes disrupt the function of limbic circuits without causing overt tissue damage, so that functional impairment precedes structural damage(63).

In animals, the most common early finding can be a change in risk assessment behavior (a behavior that is highly regulated in a healthy animal) that is the product of the interaction of the amygdala, hippocampus, and prefrontal cortex(64). However, in the presence of infection, the regulation of this network may be disrupted. Studies show that the parasite directly targets limbic GABAergic neurons and prefrontal glutamatergic neurons, causing a change in the inhibitory/excitatory balance of the network, that can show decreased caution, increased unusual curiosity, decreased response to threat, or, conversely, increased aimless avoidance and escape in behavior. In other words, "threat processing" may be the first function to be disrupted by the parasite's evolutionary tendency to change the host's behavior(65).

At the same time, subclinical disorders in the immune-neuronal axis play a key role. In the early stages, a mild but persistent increase in interleukin-6 (IL-6) and tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) together with microglia activation can induce a state of low-grade neuroinflammation, resulting in changes in synaptic plasticity and neuronal rhythms(66,67). This mild inflammation may represent intermittent irritability, reduced social tolerance, and sleep disturbance, changes in vocalization patterns, or unusual sensory responses(68).

4.3 Rabies

Rabies is a viral disease causing encephalitis(69). *Lyssavirus rabies* may change neural circuit function before substantial pathological damage becomes evident, and this feature

makes it one of the examples that can offer this hypothesis that behavioral changes occur earlier than visible clinical signs(70). The rabies neurotropic virus enters the nervous system by using retrograde axonal transport, but unlike many neurotropic pathogens, it does not stimulate a strong immune response in the early stages; for this reason, the development of structural damage in the brain may occur later, but neuronal dysfunction can begin earlier(71). This distinction between "dysfunction without damage" may be one of the main reasons for the emergence of preclinical behavioral changes(72). The virus may accumulate mainly in limbic structures (amygdala, hippocampus, and hypothalamic regions that regulate emotion, motivation, social behavior, and control sensory-cognitive responses) during this period(73).

The disruptions in these circuits may not necessarily relate to tissue damage. Studies have shown that in some cases before the onset of neuronal inflammation, changes in neurotransmitters, including glutamate, GABA, and cholinergic pathways, may occur(74). These subtle changes in synaptic function may cause some changes in behavior (such as increased excitability, decreased fear thresholds, motor restlessness, sleep disturbance, abnormal sensory sensitivities, and emotional instability)(75,76). These changes can begin before the clinical phase in some cases, and during this period, no classic signs such as dysphagia, paralysis, and hypersalivation are yet observable(77). This feature makes rabies in the pet model a valuable example for studying "sentinel behavioral deviation", suggesting its suitability for investigating behavior as an early biomarker of zoonotic disease.

4.4 Leishmaniasis

Leishmania infantum is an intramacrophage protozoan that is usually associated with long periods of subclinical infection in companion animals, especially dogs(78). During this period, the parasite can indirectly affect the central nervous system (CNS) without causing clinical symptoms because of its persistent presence in reticuloendothelial tissues, without extensive brain involvement(79,80). In the early stages, when the parasite is mostly present in the skin and lymph nodes, a specific combination of cytokines (especially IL-1 β , TNF- α , and IFN- γ) intermittently enters the bloodstream and, without structural damage, makes the blood-brain barrier (BBB) more functionally permeable(81). As a result, microglia enter a primed state (a state in which the cells are not yet fully activated but their threshold for responding to stimuli is lowered)(82). The priming of microglia on the other hand may change behavioral patterns(83). At the same time, the peripheral inflammation caused by

leishmaniasis alters the HPA axis(84). The sustained increase in corticosterone/cortisol and the change in its diurnal rhythm can affect limbic circuits; as a result, a decrease in pleasure-seeking behavior, reduced motor motivation, and the appearance of a kind of “behavioral fatigue” can be probable.(85–87).

In particular, the neuroimmune model of leishmaniasis has the potential to introduce the companion animals as sentinel hosts for controlling zoonoses.

4.5 African trypanosomiasis

The hemophagous protozoan *Trypanosoma brucei* is transmitted through the bite of the tsetse fly(88). Recently, studies on animal models showed that the causative agent of this disease can cause neurological disorders, sleep disorders, and cognitive changes through profound changes in the neuro-immune axes and behavioral regulatory systems before directly penetrating the central nervous system(89).

The parasite, by releasing variant surface genes (VSGs) in the early stages, leads to a periodic increase in proinflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IFN- γ (90). Inflammatory episodes, in turn, can usually accompanied by microglia activation and altered sensitivity of hypothalamic neurons(91).

In infected companion animals, including dogs, that are present in or travel to endemic areas, behavioral changes have been detected(92). Some research has shown that *T. brucei* can also affect host behavior when it is established in the dermis and adipose tissue, before entering the bloodstream and infecting the CNS, suggesting this zoonosis as a prominent candidate for studies of early behavioral patterns as early detection biomarkers(93).

5. Comparative Insights across Candidate Diseases

Reviewing the selected diseases revealed that, based on the available literature and despite the diversity of pathogens, there are indications that in the early phases of infection, some recurring behavioral tendencies may be observed, including decreased social interaction, altered eating and drinking patterns, lethargy, and changes in daily activities in companion animals.

A common feature suggested across several of these zoonoses is the potential presence of early neuroimmune activation, even when clinical signs are not yet apparent. Such early immune-neural interactions may contribute to subtle behavioral deviations, making behavior a possible non-invasive window into the preclinical phase of infection. However, empirical evidence remains limited, and these interpretations should be considered exploratory.

In contrast, some behavioral patterns appear more pathogen-specific, reflecting differences in neurobiological pathways and immune mechanisms—for example, fear- or anxiety-related changes that are described differently in rabies compared to the cognitive and risk-taking alterations associated with toxoplasmosis.

These pathogen-linked distinctions suggest that behavioral signatures could, in theory, support differential detection, although systematic evidence is still emerging.

Despite both the shared and pathogen-specific behavioral elements, these observations collectively indicate a rationale for developing structured ethograms and comparative behavioral protocols. With careful monitoring and standardized documentation, these candidate diseases could help shape a preliminary framework for early-behavioral evaluation of zoonoses, paving the way for interdisciplinary studies and future development of early-warning surveillance tools within the One Health framework.

6. Implications for Clinical Practice in Veterinary Medicine

By understanding the early behaviors that may be associated with zoonotic diseases, veterinarians can potentially identify animals at risk and implement preventive measures or therapeutic interventions more quickly using standardized behavioral ethograms.

Informing and educating owners as primary observers is crucial and essential. Recognizing these possible behavioral patterns can reduce clinic visit times and may facilitate timely diagnosis.

Creating clinical protocols and setting up simple questionnaires, including daily behavioral checklists and training for veterinary staff and owners, can serve as a complementary and accessible tool for early disease monitoring and may help improve the quality of animal care while reducing the risk of transmission to humans.

The convergence of behavioral science and clinical veterinary medicine within the One Health framework can provide a foundation for strengthening preventive management and risk reduction of zoonoses at the individual and community levels.

7. Conceptual Boundaries and Limitations

The behavior of companion animals as primary biomarkers of zoonoses also faces limitations that must be taken into account when interpreting behaviors.

Environmental, individual, and species factors make studying behaviors challenging, and without considering these variables, the likelihood of error in early interpretation of the disease increases.

Conceptually, a precise definition of behaviors that could be indicative of zoonoses is essential to distinguish them from behavioral changes that are simply a reflection of stress or environmental conditions.

Therefore, although the clinical and epidemiological promise of this approach is high, the natural limitations of behavior, the time-consuming nature of studies in this field, and the need for a clear conceptual framework and valid measurement protocols to achieve more reliable results are among the main challenges in this field.

8. Conceptual Model

The model proposed in this paper illustrates a hypothetical stepwise relationship between subclinical infections, neuroimmune responses, and behavioral changes in companion animals.

After pathogen entry and subclinical infection, innate immunity is activated through receptors, potentially leading to the initiation of immune responses and increased cytokine production. Subsequently, microglia priming and immune signaling may activate the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis and initiate neurotransmitter changes. Simultaneously with the tryptophan-kynurenine shift and glial activation, changes in the sensory and cognitive systems may occur, which in turn may contribute to early warning behaviors that can be recognized before clinical signs appear. (Figure 2)

Fig. 2. An integrative conceptual model for potential behavioral biomarkers in zoonotic diseases.

Discussion

Understanding the possibility that companion animals can show the first reflection of pathophysiological changes caused by zoonotic infections through their behavior opens up new horizons in the management of zoonoses at both the individual and collective levels. The findings of the present review suggest that neuroimmunological pathways, including the activation of the hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal axis, peripheral inflammation with cytokine signaling to the brain, and alterations in limbic and sensory networks, may be coherently involved in the formation of early behavioral patterns, behaviors that can potentially precede the appearance of measurable physiological signs.

A review of the evidence for diseases such as influenza, toxoplasmosis, rabies, leishmaniasis, and trypanosomiasis has suggested that behavioral changes, especially in the early days of infection, are probable.

This conceptual study aimed to argue that behaviors are not simply reflections of local abnormalities but are the result of a complex dialogue between the immune system and the brain in which the animal activates adaptive behavioral strategies in an attempt to restore homeostasis. However, these patterns in domestic animals are not just evolutionary adaptive responses but can also be practical indicators for early warning of danger to humans and the environment. This aspect places their importance beyond the scope of individual biomedicine and within the One Health framework.

Despite this potential, the lack of standard protocols for recording and interpreting behavior in domestic animals and the limited studies on the neuroimmunity of zoonotic pathogens and their action on the CNS and subsequently behavior in the early stages of infection are major challenges. Ethograms, or standardized behavioral models, could fill this gap; however, their development and validation require convergence between behavioral veterinary medicine, neuroscience, epidemiology, and data science. Another issue is the heterogeneity in sensitivity across breeds, ages, and housing environments, which may confound the interpretation of behavior. Therefore, the establishment of multicenter and longitudinal data banks is essential to distinguish natural behavioral variation from pathological changes.

From a practical perspective, the integration of behavioral indicators into national zoonoses surveillance systems would be a low-cost, non-invasive tool and particularly valuable in resource-limited countries. However, to achieve this goal, policies need to reflect the role of companion animals as early warning receivers. This requires that policymakers, including the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH) and the World Health Organization (WHO),

revise surveillance frameworks to include behavior as an independent layer of surveillance, rather than a sub-feature or subjective one.

Critically but constructively, it must be acknowledged that there is still a long way to go before reliable algorithms for early detection are available. Limitations related to the quality of owner reports, the lack of standardized digital methods for recording behavior, and the lack of large-scale, longitudinal studies are among the serious gaps in this direction. However, the substantial body of neurobiological evidence in this review suggests that scientific and policy investment in this area is not only justified but also likely to be a transformative path in zoonoses control.

Conclusion

The present conceptual review proposes that behavior in companion animals, as a rapid and observable feature that may reflect early neuroimmunological changes induced by zoonotic infections, has the potential to serve as an early and practical biomarker. This perspective introduces a novel and interdisciplinary approach to zoonoses surveillance that could help narrow the gap between the onset of pathology and the eventual point of diagnosis. However, realizing this potential will require standardization of behavioral observation methods, improved owner education, development of digital behavior-tracking tools, and the implementation of longitudinal and multicenter studies.

Future perspectives

Given the prominent role of behavior in the early detection of zoonotic diseases, the future of this field requires a combination of macroscopic approaches and practical solutions. At the upstream level, it is necessary to develop studies that can standardize the natural range of behavioral patterns across different species, as this basic information can help design early detection protocols and create integrated behavioral data banks. Further investment in interdisciplinary research, particularly collaborations between behaviorists, epidemiologists, public health specialists, and data scientists, could provide more refined frameworks for using behavioral indicators as predictive tools. In addition, simple yet effective clinical interventions are also important; producing brochures and educational tools for pet owners, promoting a culture of attention to subtle behavioral changes, and using behavioral checklists in routine examinations can serve as an early warning system at the clinic level. Combining these two macroscopic and practical approaches paves the way for a more comprehensive framework for integrating behavioral indicators into One Health surveillance models.

References

1. World Health Organization RO for the EM. Zoonotic diseases [Internet]. 2025. Available from: <https://www.emro.who.int/about-who/rc61/zoonotic-diseases.html>
2. Esposito MM, Turku S, Lehrfield L, Shoman A. The Impact of Human Activities on Zoonotic Infection Transmissions. *Anim an open access J from MDPI*. 2023 May;13(10).
3. Giannelli A, Schnyder M, Wright I, Charlier J. Control of companion animal parasites and impact on One Health. *One Heal (Amsterdam, Netherlands)*. 2024 Jun;18:100679.
4. Schwarz NG, Loderstaedt U, Hahn A, Hinz R, Zautner AE, Eibach D, et al. Microbiological laboratory diagnostics of neglected zoonotic diseases (NZDs). *Acta Trop*. 2017 Jan;165:40–65.
5. Nicol CJ. Behavioural indicators of infectious disease in managed animals. *Appl Anim Behav Sci [Internet]*. 2025;285:106573. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0168159125000711>
6. Castaño Barrios L, Da Silva Pinheiro AP, Gibaldi D, Silva AA, Machado Rodrigues E Silva P, Roffê E, et al. Behavioral alterations in long-term *Toxoplasma gondii* infection of C57BL/6 mice are associated with neuroinflammation and disruption of the blood brain barrier. *PLoS One*. 2021;16(10):e0258199.
7. Aggarwal D, Ramachandran A. One Health Approach to Address Zoonotic Diseases. *Indian J community Med Off Publ Indian Assoc Prev Soc Med*. 2020 Mar;45(Suppl 1):S6–8.
8. Morelle K, Barasona JA, Bosch J, Heine G, Daim A, Arnold J, et al. Accelerometer-based detection of African swine fever infection in wild boar. *Proceedings Biol Sci*. 2023 Aug;290(2005):20231396.
9. Pinello KC, Palmieri C, Ruiz J, Zaidan Dagli ML, Niza-Ribeiro J. Chapter 4 - Risks and benefits of the interaction with companion animals. In: Prata JC, Ribeiro AI, Rocha-Santos TBTOH, editors. Academic Press; 2022. p. 113–53. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780128227947000125>
10. Ramezani Gardaloud N, Guse C, Lidauer L, Steininger A, Kicking F, Öhlschuster M, et al. Early Detection of Respiratory Diseases in Calves by Use of an Ear-Attached Accelerometer. *Anim an open access J from MDPI*. 2022 Apr;12(9).
11. Kosmider RD, Kelly L, Simons RL, Brouwer A, David G. Detecting new and emerging diseases on livestock farms using an early detection system. *Epidemiol Infect*. 2011 Oct;139(10):1476–85.
12. Krapić M, Kavazović I, Wensveen FM. Immunological Mechanisms of Sickness Behavior in Viral Infection. *Viruses*. 2021 Nov;13(11).
13. Devlin BA, Smith CJ, Bilbo SD. Sickness and the Social Brain: How the Immune System Regulates Behavior across Species. *Brain Behav Evol*. 2022;97(3–4):197–210.
14. Lopes PC, French SS, Woodhams DC, Binning SA. Sickness behaviors across vertebrate taxa: proximate and ultimate mechanisms. *J Exp Biol*. 2021 May;224(9).
15. Sullivan ZA, Dulac C. Sickness and the brain. *Curr Biol [Internet]*. 2025 Oct

20;35(20):R973–9. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2025.08.050>

16. Shattuck EC, Boyle CC. Introduction to the special issue: evolutionary and biopsychosocial perspectives on sickness communication. *Evol Med public Heal*. 2024;12(1):71–4.
17. Selyemová D, Antolová D, Mangová B, Jarošová J, Ličková M, Havlíková SF, et al. Cats as a sentinel species for human infectious diseases - toxoplasmosis, trichinellosis, and COVID-19. *Curr Res Parasitol vector-borne Dis*. 2024;6:100196.
18. Bowser NH, Anderson NE. Dogs (*Canis familiaris*) as Sentinels for Human Infectious Disease and Application to Canadian Populations: A Systematic Review. *Vet Sci*. 2018 Sep;5(4).
19. Duxbury MM, Sobczynski H, Flynn K, Rendahl A. A behavior screening questionnaire improves problem identification in veterinary primary care with implications for patient health. *J Am Vet Med Assoc*. 2024 Apr;262(4):1–9.
20. Hegedus C, Andronie L, Uiuu P, Jurco E, Lazar EA, Popescu S. Pets, Genuine Tools of Environmental Pollutant Detection. *Anim an open access J from MDPI*. 2023 Sep;13(18).
21. Sohn-Hausner N, Kmetiuk LB, da Silva EC, Langoni H, Biondo AW. One Health Approach to Leptospirosis: Dogs as Environmental Sentinels for Identification and Monitoring of Human Risk Areas in Southern Brazil. *Trop Med Infect Dis*. 2023 Sep;8(9).
22. Gamble A, Olarte-Castillo XA, Whittaker GR. Backyard zoonoses: The roles of companion animals and peri-domestic wildlife. *Sci Transl Med*. 2023 Oct;15(718):eadj0037.
23. Dantzer R. Evolutionary Aspects of Infections: Inflammation and Sickness Behaviors. *Curr Top Behav Neurosci*. 2023;61:1–14.
24. Singh H, Koury J, Kaul M. Innate Immune Sensing of Viruses and Its Consequences for the Central Nervous System. *Viruses*. 2021 Jan;13(2).
25. Jagot F, Gaston-Breton R, Choi AJ, Pascal M, Bourhy L, Dorado-Doncel R, et al. The parabrachial nucleus elicits a vigorous corticosterone feedback response to the pro-inflammatory cytokine IL-1 β . *Neuron*. 2023 Aug;111(15):2367-2382.e6.
26. Miyata S. Glial functions in the blood-brain communication at the circumventricular organs. *Front Neurosci*. 2022;16:991779.
27. Miller AH, Haroon E, Raison CL, Felger JC. Cytokine targets in the brain: impact on neurotransmitters and neurocircuits. *Depress Anxiety*. 2013 Apr;30(4):297–306.
28. Kurki SN, Ala-Kurikka T, Lipponen A, Pospelov AS, Roloova T, Koistinaho J, et al. A brain cytokine-independent switch in cortical activity marks the onset of sickness behavior triggered by acute peripheral inflammation. *J Neuroinflammation*. 2023 Jul;20(1):176.
29. Li X, Li X, Zhang Q, Li Y, Zhou Y, Zhou J, et al. Prostaglandin endoperoxide synthase 2 regulates neuroinflammation to mediate postoperative cognitive dysfunction in mice. *Sci Rep [Internet]*. 2025;15(1):17355. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-01121-z>

30. Mittli D. Inflammatory processes in the prefrontal cortex induced by systemic immune challenge: Focusing on neurons. *Brain, Behav Immun - Heal.* 2023 Dec;34:100703.
31. Zhang G, Yao Q, Long C, Yi P, Song J, Wu L, et al. Infiltration by monocytes of the central nervous system and its role in multiple sclerosis: reflections on therapeutic strategies. *Neural Regen Res.* 2025 Mar;20(3):779–93.
32. Lei AA, Phang VW, Lee YZ, Kow AS, Tham CL, Ho YC, et al. Chronic Stress-Associated Depressive Disorders: The Impact of HPA Axis Dysregulation and Neuroinflammation on the Hippocampus—A Mini Review. Vol. 26, *International Journal of Molecular Sciences.* 2025. p. 2940.
33. Balakin E, Yurku K, Ivanov M, Izotov A, Nakhod V, Pustovoyt V. Regulation of Stress-Induced Immunosuppression in the Context of Neuroendocrine, Cytokine, and Cellular Processes. Vol. 14, *Biology.* 2025. p. 76.
34. Mehay D, Silberman Y, Arnold AC. The Arcuate Nucleus of the Hypothalamus and Metabolic Regulation: An Emerging Role for Renin-Angiotensin Pathways. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2021 Jun;22(13).
35. Lightman SL, Birnie MT, Conway-Campbell BL. Dynamics of ACTH and Cortisol Secretion and Implications for Disease. *Endocr Rev.* 2020 Jun;41(3).
36. Hu P, Lu Y, Pan BX, Zhang WH. New Insights into the Pivotal Role of the Amygdala in Inflammation-Related Depression and Anxiety Disorder. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2022 Sep;23(19).
37. Guthrie M. The mesolimbic dopamine pathway: reward circuitry and psychiatric disorders. *Cogn Neurosci J.* 2024;7(3):215.
38. Felger JC, Treadway MT. Inflammation Effects on Motivation and Motor Activity: Role of Dopamine. *Neuropsychopharmacol Off Publ Am Coll Neuropsychopharmacol.* 2017 Jan;42(1):216–41.
39. Jiang X, Xu L, Tang L, Liu F, Chen Z, Zhang J, et al. Role of the indoleamine-2,3-dioxygenase/kynurenine pathway of tryptophan metabolism in behavioral alterations in a hepatic encephalopathy rat model. *J Neuroinflammation.* 2018 Jan;15(1):3.
40. Chen LM, Bao CH, Wu Y, Liang SH, Wang D, Wu LY, et al. Tryptophan-kynurenine metabolism: a link between the gut and brain for depression in inflammatory bowel disease. *J Neuroinflammation.* 2021 Jun;18(1):135.
41. Cheng J, Zheng B, Luo S, Yuan Y, Wu X, Jiang Z, et al. Argon improves microglia-mediated hippocampal neuronal hyperexcitability to alleviate anxiety-like behaviors in mice. *J Mol Cell Biol.* 2025 Nov;17(4).
42. Müller L, Di Benedetto S. Neuroimmune crosstalk in chronic neuroinflammation: microglial interactions and immune modulation. *Front Cell Neurosci.* 2025;19:1575022.
43. Prossin AR, Zalcman SS, Heitzeg MM, Koch AE, Campbell PL, Phan KL, et al. Dynamic interactions between plasma IL-1 family cytokines and central endogenous opioid neurotransmitter function in humans. *Neuropsychopharmacol Off Publ Am Coll Neuropsychopharmacol.* 2015 Feb;40(3):554–65.
44. Cantini D, Choleris E, Kavaliers M. Neurobiology of Pathogen Avoidance and Mate

- Choice: Current and Future Directions. *Anim* an open access J from MDPI. 2024 Jan;14(2).
45. Boillat M, Hammoudi PM, Dogga SK, Pagès S, Goubran M, Rodriguez I, et al. Neuroinflammation-Associated Aspecific Manipulation of Mouse Predator Fear by *Toxoplasma gondii*. *Cell Rep*. 2020 Jan;30(2):320-334.e6.
 46. Poon DCH, Ho YS, Chiu K, Wong HL, Chang RCC. Sickness: From the focus on cytokines, prostaglandins, and complement factors to the perspectives of neurons. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev*. 2015 Oct;57:30–45.
 47. Stanton LA, Sullivan MS, Fazio JM. A standardized ethogram for the felidae: A tool for behavioral researchers. *Appl Anim Behav Sci* [Internet]. 2015;173:3–16. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0168159115001008>
 48. Zhou S, Li W, Zhou M, Dilger RN, Condotta ICFS, Wu Z, et al. Foundations of Livestock Behavioral Recognition: Ethogram Analysis of Behavioral Definitions and Its Practices in Multimodal Large Language Models. *Anim* an open access J from MDPI. 2025 Oct;15(20).
 49. Bauer L, Benavides FFW, Veldhuis Kroeze EJB, de Wit E, van Riel D. The neuropathogenesis of highly pathogenic avian influenza H5Nx viruses in mammalian species including humans. *Trends Neurosci* [Internet]. 2023;46(11):953–70. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S016622362300190X>
 50. Ciruela P, Soldevila N, Torner N, Basile L, Mosquera MDM, Marcos MA, et al. Acute Influenza Virus-Associated Encephalitis and Other Neurological Complications in Severe Hospitalized Laboratory-Confirmed Influenza Cases-Catalonia 2010-2020. *Pathog* (Basel, Switzerland). 2025 Feb;14(3).
 51. Plaza PI, Gamarra-Toledo V, Euguí JR, Lambertucci SA. Recent Changes in Patterns of Mammal Infection with Highly Pathogenic Avian Influenza A(H5N1) Virus Worldwide. *Emerg Infect Dis*. 2024 Mar;30(3):444–52.
 52. Siegers JY, van den Brand JM, Leijten LM, van de Bildt MMW, van Run PR, van Amerongen G, et al. Vaccination Is More Effective Than Prophylactic Oseltamivir in Preventing CNS Invasion by H5N1 Virus via the Olfactory Nerve. *J Infect Dis*. 2016 Aug;214(4):516–24.
 53. Reperant LA, van Amerongen G, van de Bildt MWG, Rimmelzwaan GF, Dobson AP, Osterhaus ADME, et al. Highly pathogenic avian influenza virus (H5N1) infection in red foxes fed infected bird carcasses. *Emerg Infect Dis*. 2008 Dec;14(12):1835–41.
 54. Haman KH, Pearson SF, Brown J, Frisbie LA, Penhallegon S, Falghoush AM, et al. A comprehensive epidemiological approach documenting an outbreak of H5N1 highly pathogenic avian influenza virus clade 2.3.4.4b among gulls, terns, and harbor seals in the Northeastern Pacific. *Front Vet Sci*. 2024;11:1483922.
 55. Ly H. Highly pathogenic avian influenza H5N1 virus infection of companion animals. Vol. 15, *Virulence*. United States; 2024. p. 2289780.
 56. Tammiranta N, Isomursu M, Fusaro A, Nylund M, Nokireki T, Giussani E, et al. Highly pathogenic avian influenza A (H5N1) virus infections in wild carnivores connected to mass mortalities of pheasants in Finland. *Infect Genet Evol* [Internet]. 2023;111:105423. Available from:

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1567134823000217>

57. Murawski A, Fabrizio T, Ossiboff R, Kackos C, Jeevan T, Jones JC, et al. Highly pathogenic avian influenza A(H5N1) virus in a common bottlenose dolphin (*Tursiops truncatus*) in Florida. *Commun Biol*. 2024 Apr;7(1):476.
58. De Conto F. Avian Influenza A Viruses Modulate the Cellular Cytoskeleton during Infection of Mammalian Hosts. *Pathog (Basel, Switzerland)*. 2024 Mar;13(3).
59. Portes J, Barrias E, Travassos R, Attias M, de Souza W. *Toxoplasma gondii* Mechanisms of Entry Into Host Cells. *Front Cell Infect Microbiol*. 2020;10:294.
60. Cudjoe O, Afful R, Hagan TA. *Toxoplasma*–host endoplasmic reticulum interaction: How *T. gondii* activates unfolded protein response and modulates immune response. *Curr Res Microb Sci* [Internet]. 2024;6:100223. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666517424000051>
61. Ramírez-Flores CJ, Mondragón-Flores R. Comprehensive analysis of *Toxoplasma gondii* migration routes and tissue dissemination in the host. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*. 2025 Jul;19(7):e0013369.
62. Tabaie EZ, Gao Z, Kachour N, Ulu A, Gomez S, Figueroa ZA, et al. *Toxoplasma gondii* infection of neurons alters the production and content of extracellular vesicles directing astrocyte phenotype and contributing to the loss of GLT-1 in the infected brain. *PLoS Pathog*. 2025 Jun;21(6):e1012733.
63. Mouveaux T, Roger E, Gueye A, Eysert F, Huot L, Grenier-Boley B, et al. Primary brain cell infection by *Toxoplasma gondii* reveals the extent and dynamics of parasite differentiation and its impact on neuron biology. *Open Biol*. 2021 Oct;11(10):210053.
64. Ihara F, Nishimura M, Muroi Y, Mahmoud ME, Yokoyama N, Nagamune K, et al. *Toxoplasma gondii* Infection in Mice Impairs Long-Term Fear Memory Consolidation through Dysfunction of the Cortex and Amygdala. *Infect Immun*. 2016 Oct;84(10):2861–70.
65. Latifi A, Flegr J. Beyond Latency: Chronic *Toxoplasma* Infection and Its Unveiled Behavioral and Clinical Manifestations—A 30-Year Research Perspective. Vol. 13, *Biomedicines*. 2025. p. 1731.
66. Cowan MN, Sethi I, Harris TH. Microglia in CNS infections: insights from *Toxoplasma gondii* and other pathogens. *Trends Parasitol*. 2022 Mar;38(3):217–29.
67. Moghaddami R, Mahdipour M, Ahmadpour E. Inflammatory pathways of *Toxoplasma gondii* infection in pregnancy. *Travel Med Infect Dis* [Internet]. 2024;62:102760. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1477893924000772>
68. Desmettre T. Toxoplasmosis and behavioural changes. *J Fr Ophtalmol* [Internet]. 2020;43(3):e89–93. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S018155122030022X>
69. Palii D, Mohnii H, Voinalovych O. Rabies Clinical Perspective: Case Description and Care Strategies. *Fam Med Eur Pract*. 2024 Feb 29;52–6.
70. Kim S, Larrous F, Varet H, Legendre R, Feige L, Dumas G, et al. Early Transcriptional Changes in Rabies Virus-Infected Neurons and Their Impact on

- Neuronal Functions. *Front Microbiol.* 2021;12:730892.
71. Wongchitrat P, Chanmee T, Govitrapong P. Molecular Mechanisms Associated with Neurodegeneration of Neurotropic Viral Infection. *Mol Neurobiol* [Internet]. 2024;61(5):2881–903. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12035-023-03761-6>
 72. Hueffer K, Khatri S, Rideout S, Harris MB, Papke RL, Stokes C, et al. Rabies virus modifies host behaviour through a snake-toxin like region of its glycoprotein that inhibits neurotransmitter receptors in the CNS. *Sci Rep* [Internet]. 2017;7(1):12818. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-12726-4>
 73. Mohindra R, Madhav M, Suri V, Divyashree K. Limbic system symptoms of rabies infection. *BMJ Case Rep.* 2022 Jul;15(7).
 74. Bastos V, Pacheco V, Rodrigues ÉDL, Moraes CNS, Nóbile AL, Fonseca DLM, et al. Neuroimmunology of rabies: New insights into an ancient disease. *J Med Virol.* 2023 Oct;95(10):e29042.
 75. Kaczmarek P, Sochal M, Strzelecki D, Białasiewicz P, Gabryelska A. Influence of glutamatergic and GABAergic neurotransmission on obstructive sleep apnea. *Front Neurosci.* 2023;17:1213971.
 76. Purkayastha P, Malapati A, Yogeeswari P, Sriram D. A Review on GABA/Glutamate Pathway for Therapeutic Intervention of ASD and ADHD. *Curr Med Chem.* 2015 May;22(15):1850–9.
 77. Hemachudha T, Ugolini G, Wacharapluesadee S, Sungkarat W, Shuangshoti S, Laothamatas J. Human rabies: neuropathogenesis, diagnosis, and management. *Lancet Neurol.* 2013 May;12(5):498–513.
 78. Hide M, Michel G, Legueult K, Pin R, Leonard S, Simon L, et al. Asymptomatic *Leishmania infantum* infection in dogs and dog owners in an endemic area in southeast France. *Parasite.* 2024 Mar 26;31:16.
 79. Petersen CA, Greenlee MHW. Neurologic Manifestations of *Leishmania* spp. Infection. *J Neuroparasitology.* 2011;2.
 80. Maia C, Monteiro M, Gavioli E, Oliveira F, Oliveira G, Romão P. Neurological disease in human and canine leishmaniasis - clinical features and immunopathogenesis. *Parasite Immunol.* 2015 May 1;37.
 81. Melo GD, Goyard S, Fiette L, Boissonnas A, Combadiere C, Machado GF, et al. Unveiling Cerebral Leishmaniasis: parasites and brain inflammation in *Leishmania donovani* infected mice. *Sci Rep.* 2017 Aug;7(1):8454.
 82. Calvo Alvarez E, Sfogliarini C, La Rosa F, Saresella M, Dolci M, Vegeto E, et al. Immune subversion by *Leishmania infantum* parasites suppresses NLRP3-driven inflammatory responses in amyloid- β -activated microglia. *J Neuroinflammation.* 2025 Oct;22(1):252.
 83. Rohan Walker F, Yirmiya R. Microglia, physiology and behavior: A brief commentary. *Brain Behav Immun* [Internet]. 2016;55:1–5. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0889159116300514>
 84. Barros-Gonçalves T de D, Saavedra AF, Silva-Couto L da, Ribeiro-Romão RP, Bezerra-Paiva M, Gomes-Silva A, et al. Increased levels of cortisol are associated with

- the severity of experimental visceral leishmaniasis in a *Leishmania (L.) infantum*-hamster model. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*. 2021 Nov;15(11):e0009987.
85. Knezevic E, Nenic K, Milanovic V, Knezevic NN. The Role of Cortisol in Chronic Stress, Neurodegenerative Diseases, and Psychological Disorders. Vol. 12, *Cells*. 2023. p. 2726.
 86. Chen C, Xiong B, Tan W, Tian Y, Zhang S, Wu J, et al. Setting the tone for the day: Cortisol awakening response proactively modulates fronto-limbic circuitry for emotion processing. *Neuroimage* [Internet]. 2025;315:121251. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S105381192500254X>
 87. Mârza SM, Munteanu C, Papuc I, Radu L, Diana P, Purdoiu RC. Behavioral, Physiological, and Pathological Approaches of Cortisol in Dogs. *Anim an open access J from MDPI*. 2024 Dec;14(23).
 88. Boundenga L, Mombo IM, Augustin MO, Barthélémy N, Nzassi PM, Moukodoum ND, et al. Molecular Identification of Trypanosome Diversity in Domestic Animals Reveals the Presence of *Trypanosoma brucei gambiense* in Historical Foci of Human African Trypanosomiasis in Gabon. *Pathog (Basel, Switzerland)*. 2022 Aug;11(9).
 89. Adebisi OE, Omobowale TO, Abatan MO. Neurocognitive domains and neuropathological changes in experimental infection with *Trypanosoma brucei brucei* in Wistar rats. *Heliyon*. 2021 Nov;7(11):e08260.
 90. Machado H, Bizarra-Rebello T, Costa-Sequeira M, Trindade S, Carvalho T, Rijo-Ferreira F, et al. *Trypanosoma brucei* triggers a broad immune response in the adipose tissue. *PLoS Pathog*. 2021 Sep;17(9):e1009933.
 91. Uzcatogui NL, Güçer S, Richter C, Speidel A, Zirdum E, Duszenko M, et al. Live imaging of microglia during sleeping sickness reveals early and heterogeneous inflammatory responses. *Front Immunol*. 2023;14:1253648.
 92. Nwoha R, Boniface A. Clinical Effects of Mixed Infection of Trypanosomes and *Ancylostoma caninum* in Dogs and Treatment with Diminazene and Mebendazole (Nigeria). *Br J Med Med Res*. 2016 Jan 10;11:1–10.
 93. Crilly NP, Mugnier MR. Thinking outside the blood: Perspectives on tissue-resident *Trypanosoma brucei*. *PLoS Pathog*. 2021 Sep;17(9):e1009866.
 94. Senay TE, Ferrell JL, Garrett FG, Albrecht TM, Cho J, Alexander KL, et al. Neurotropic Lineage III Strains of *Listeria monocytogenes* Disseminate to the Brain without Reaching High Titer in the Blood. *mSphere*. 2020 Sep;5(5).
 95. Wei P, Bao R, Fan Y. Brainstem Encephalitis Caused by *Listeria monocytogenes*. *Pathog (Basel, Switzerland)*. 2020 Aug;9(9).
 96. Vasconcelos M, Moreira AP, Pereira CS, Duarte Armindo R, Noronha C. Brain Abscess Caused by *Listeria monocytogenes*: A Rare Case of Supratentorial Neurolisteriosis. *Cureus*. 2024 Feb;16(2):e54521.
 97. Remuzgo-Martínez S, Pilares-Ortega L, Icardo JM, Valdizán EM, Vargas VI, Pazos A, et al. Microglial activation and expression of immune-related genes in a rat *ex vivo* nervous system model after infection with *Listeria monocytogenes*. *Glia*. 2013 Apr;61(4):611–22.

98. Jaguezski AM, Perin G, Rhoden LA, da Silva TMA, Mendes RE, Bottari NB, et al. Changes on the activity of cholinesterase's in an immunomodulatory response of cattle infected by *Listeria monocytogenes*. *Microb Pathog* [Internet]. 2018;114:36–40. Available from:
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0882401017311920>
99. Latorre E, Pradilla-Dieste A, Chueca B, Pagán R, Layunta E, Alcalde A, et al. *Listeria monocytogenes* Inhibits Serotonin Transporter in Human Intestinal Caco-2 Cells. *Microb Ecol*. 2016 Oct 1;72.